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A STUDY ON AWARENESS AND USAGE OF SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTS AMONG THE PEOPLE IN PALAYAMKOTTAI AREA

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Abstract

Solar energy is the most readily available source of energy. It is a significant sustainable clean and green source of energy, which can help in reducing greenhouse gas emission leading to sustainable development. Solar energy devices are launched mainly with the objective to create environmental awareness of mass power consumption and the need to conserve power. The main drawback of solar products is high price and high space requirement to setup a device. Apart from these drawbacks, the customers must consider the fact that solar energy devices are highly beneficial not only for the environment but also for human beings for its unique feature of infinite abundant energy. Though most people still prefer the usage of electrical devices, the attitude of the customers is steadily changing now days. Hence the study examines the awareness and usage of solar products. The research is based on the primary data and secondary data. Primary data is collected from 150 respondents through the form of questionnaire. From this study, it can be concluded that Customer's attitude towards Solar energy devices is definitely changing due to many valid reasons and also there has been a significant increase in the awareness and benefits of using Solar energized devices over electrical devices.

Keywords : Solar energy, Solar products, awareness and usage of solar energy products.

Introduction

Solar energy is the energy that is in sunlight. It has been used for thousands of years in many different ways by people all over the world. As well as its traditional human uses in heating, cooking, and drying, it is used today to make electricity where other power supplies are absent, such as in remote places and in space. It is becoming cheaper to make electricity from solar energy and in many situations it is now competitive with energy from coal or oil. A solar cooker can be used for cooking food. Solar energy is also called "Heat Trapper".

Solar energy is the instant source of energy. There are two main types of solar energy. Solar photovoltaic (PV) panels directly convert solar energy into a usable form of energy using a PV cell containing a semiconductor material. CSP (concentrating solar power) on the other hand, concentrate energy from sunlight to a heat receiver which transforms energy from heat into mechanical energy, and in turn, solar thermal electricity. This solar energy can be used in many ways, such as domestic lighting/ heating/cooking, street light, electricity /power generation, water pumping, powering of remote telecommunication etc.,. Solar products are available in the market for

using both domestically and industrially. With the increase of Literacy and Social Responsibility in people, the Solar Energy Devices has increasing attention in the recent scenario. There has been many researches being conducted with the help of Government funds and many industries have started manufacturing different solar energy devices with the view of Electricity conservation and Eco-Friendly environment.

Advantages of Solar Power

- Solar energy is a clean and renewable energy source.
- Once a solar panel is installed, solar energy can be produced free of charge.
- Solar energy will last forever whereas it is estimated that the world's oil reserves will last for 30 to 40 years.
- Solar energy causes no pollution.
- Solar cells make absolutely no noise at all. On the other hand, the giant machines utilized for pumping oil are extremely noisy and therefore very impractical.
- Very little maintenance is needed to keep solar cells running. There are no moving parts in a solar cell which makes it impossible to really damage them.

- In the long term, there can be a high return on investment due to the amount of free energy a solar panel can produce, it is estimated that the average household will see 50% of their energy coming in from solar panels.
- 3. To understand the usage of solar products among women graduates.
- 4. To study about the customers ideas, preferences and attitude towards Solar products

Disadvantages of Solar Power

- Solar panels are expensive to install resulting in a time-lag of many years for savings on energy bills to match initial investments.
- Electricity generation depends entirely on a countries exposure to sunlight; this could be limited by a countries climate.
- Solar power stations do not match the power output of similar sized conventional power stations; they can also be very expensive to build.
- Solar power is used to charge batteries so that solar powered devices can be used at night. The batteries can often be large and heavy, taking up space and needing to be replaced from time to time.

Review of literature

Dr. M. Venkatraman and U. Sheeba (2014) in their study on "Customer's Attitude towards Solar Energy Devices" have studied the awareness of the solar energy devices and the ideas, preferences and attitude among respondents. Customer's attitude towards solar energy devices is definitely changing and there has been a significant increase in the awareness of using solar energized devices.

Anupamaa S chavan and Dr. Madhav N Welling (2013) "Assessing the Awareness of Government Subsidy for Solar Water Heaters among people of Mumbai (India)". In their study they have examined the significance of Government subsidy on the use of Solar Water Heaters. The study concluded that everyone in Mumbai is not aware of Government Subsidies/Incentives and they recommended that the manufacturers should spread awareness regarding the availability of Government Subsidy/Incentives.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand the importance of solar energy.
2. To create awareness about the solar products among women graduates.

Limitations of the study

This study was restricted to residents living in Palyamkottai alone and the result may not be very accurate as its respondents are restricted to 150.

Methodology

Collection of Data

The research is based on the primary data and secondary data. Primary data is collected from 150 respondents through the form of questionnaire and secondary data taken from magazines, journals, books and various websites.

Tools Used for Analysis

- Percentage Analysis
- Rank Analysis
- Weighted Average Analysis

Presentation, Analysis & Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic Profile

Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	87	58%
	female	63	42%
Marital status	Married	108	72%
	unmarried	42	28%
Type of family	Joint family	59	39%
	Nuclear family	91	61%
Age	Up to 25 years	40	27%
	25 to 35 years	60	40%
	35 to 45 years	30	20%
	Above 45 years	20	13%
Educational qualification	12 th	35	23%
	UG	62	41%
	PG	30	20%
	others	23	16%
Occupation	Employed	105	70%
	Unemployed	45	30%
Income per month	Up to Rs 10000	36	24%
	Rs 10000 to Rs 20000	49	33%
	Rs 20000 to Rs 30000	35	23%
	More than Rs 30000	30	20%
Members in family	Less than 3	55	37%
	3 - 5	68	45%
	More than 5	27	18%
Monthly EB bill	Less than Rs 1000	53	35%

	Rs 1000- Rs 2000	70	47%
	More than Rs 2000	27	18%
Awareness about solar products	Yes	123	82%
	No	27	18%
Information about solar energy products	Friends & family	38	25%
	Advertisements	62	41%
	Colleagues	39	26%
	Others	11	8%
Aware about	Solar water heater	93	62%
	Solar Calculator	38	25%
	Solar street lights	19	13%
Willingness to buy solar products	Yes	109	73%
	No	51	34%
Willing to buy it in	Cash	63	42%
	Credit	87	58%
Aware about government subsidy	Yes	64	43%
	No	86	57%

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.1 shows that

- Majority of the respondents are Males, Married and Live in Nuclear Families.
- Majority (40%) of the respondents are between 25 – 35 years of age.
- Majority (41%) of the respondents are under graduates.
- Most (70%) of the respondents are Employed.
- Most (32%) of the respondents have their Monthly income between Rs.10000 – 20000.
- Most (45%) of the respondents have 3 - 5 members in their family.
- Most (47%) of the respondents have their Monthly Electricity bill between Rs.1000 – 2000.
- Majority (82%) of the respondents are Aware about the Solar Energy Products.
- Majority (41%) of the respondents are aware about the Solar Energy products through Advertisements.
- Most (62%) of the respondents are aware about the Solar Water Heaters.
- Most (73%) of the respondents are willing to buy the solar energy products.
- Most (58%) of the respondents prefer to purchase solar energy products by credit.

- Majority (57%) of the respondents are not aware of government subsidies.

Table 2 Factors for switching over from electrical products to solar energy products

S.No	Factors	Weighted score	Average score	Rank
1	Status in the society	490	98	V
2	Influence of advertisement	445	89	VI
3	Low electricity bill	620	124	I
4	Environmental friendly	540	108	III
5	Durability	545	109	II
6	Safety	510	102	IV

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.2 shows that the respondents are switching over from Electrical products to solar energy products due to its low electricity bill followed by durability and environmental friendliness.

Table 3 Problems in buying solar energy products

S.No	Factors	Weighted score	average score	Rank
1	Very costly	588	117.6	I
2	High installation charges	422	84.4	VI
3	Occupy large space	562	112.4	II
4	Changing climatic condition	535	107	III
5	Lack of demonstration & exhibition	504	100.8	IV
6	Lack of varieties in solar products	480	96	V

Source: Data collected through questionnaire

The above table 5.3 shows that the respondents face the problems in buying the solar products because it is very costly, it occupies large space and due to changing climatic condition.

Suggestions

The price of the Solar Energy Devices may be considerably reduced, so that the people from low income groups can also afford to buy the Solar Energy Devices. The Solar Energy Devices can

also be made available in small size, as they consume a large space for setup. There should be awareness about the availability of the Solar Energy Devices among the people hailing from different localities, especially in rural areas and people not with proper education who doesn't have proper awareness about the use of solar energy. The installation charges of the Solar Energy Devices must be made lesser so that the customers need not worry about high Installation charges adding onto the original price of the devices. People must be made aware of the subsidies provided by the government on buying a Solar Energy Device and also the Government should take more steps in promoting Solar Energy Devices in other ways such as reducing tax etc.,

Conclusion

From this study, it can be concluded that Customer's attitude towards Solar energy devices is definitely changing due to many valid reasons and also there has been a significant increase in the awareness and benefits of using Solar energized devices over electrical devices. In this fast moving world, the consumption of energy has been increasing in abundant amount and the customers have become more conscious about saving power and switching on to other sources of power like solar energy for their consumption. This study helps in identifying the knowledge of respondents about solar products, Therefore, in order to meet the customers need the business sectors should come with innovative yet cost-benefit and new techniques in the solar market as it not only

attracts more number of customers and keeps the business intact, but also increases the consumers responsibility towards the environment and eco-friendliness for securing mother earth.

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